

**THEORETICAL DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF IMPEDANCE
BOUNDARY CONDITION CASING TREATMENT**

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ABSTRACT

A proper stall margin for the aeroengine is the key to ensuring the stable flight of the airplane. unsteady casing treatments can enhance the stall margin based on the wave-vortex interaction, and the effects can be modeled as an impedance boundary condition. This work establishes a theoretical framework for the design of the unsteady casing treatment. Specifically, this work selects a casing treatment with the slotted perforated plate and annular chamber as the case study to validate the proposed design method. Firstly, an impedance model for the perforated plate and annular chamber is developed, which correlates with geometry parameters, flow parameters, circumferential mode number and frequency. Subsequently, experiments are conducted to compare measured stall mass flow points with theoretical results, thereby validating the method. Notably, the proposed theoretical design method for unsteady casing treatments enables rapid searching and filtering of valid parameter sets. Additionally, the method establishes the relationship between impedance, energy gain, casing treatment geometry parameters and stall margin of the compressor.

Keywords: Compressor, Global stability analysis, Impedance boundary condition, Casing treatment design;

NOMENCLATURE

A, B, H, L, M	Coefficient matrix
f	Forcing term
L_s	Length of slot chord
w_s	Slot width
q	Flow perturbation parameter

r, R	resistance
x, X	reactance
y	Response term
Z	Acoustic impedance
ρ	Density
ω	Characteristic frequency
θ_s	Left boundary
θ_p	Right boundary

1. INTRODUCTION

In the field of aeronautical engineering, modern aero-engine design increasingly demands higher thrust-to-weight ratios, posing substantial challenges on compressor developments. under off-design conditions, the need for elevated blade loading has heightened the susceptibility of the compressor to rotating stall and surge, critical instabilities that threaten compressor integrity and engine performance. Rotating stall is an unstable, low-amplitude flow phenomenon typically occurring within rotor rotating frequency (RRF) range, which always results in a sudden drop of rotor blade loading. This phenomenon is often coupled with surge, a low-frequency, high-amplitude axial flow oscillation that can cause irreversible damage to compressors, and even entire engines. Researchers have developed numerous strategies to enhance compressor stall margin (SM), which fall broadly into active and passive control methods. Among these passive approaches, casing treatment (CT) has emerged as one of the most effective solutions.

Despite extensive engineering and academic investigations, a universally applicable, cost-efficient, and reliable CT design methodology remains elusive. Some researchers [1,2]

transformed CT design as geometric optimization problem based on the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and machine learning. Despite extensive engineering and academic investigations, a universally applicable, cost-efficient, and reliable CT design methodology remains elusive. While these approaches have demonstrated improvements in SM, their efficacy is heavily constrained by two key limitations: surrogate models and numerical simulation. Additionally, they require extensive steady and unsteady numerical computations. Furthermore, dimensional explosion poses an acute challenge when optimizing many geometric parameters simultaneously.

Notably, Houghton and Day [3] identified discrepancies between numerical simulations and experiments for circumferential grooved CTs: steady numerical simulations overestimated SM improvements at certain installation positions, predicting maximum gains in regions where experiments showed minimal or no benefit. The physics of stall inception cannot be captured by steady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes simulations, which should not be trusted to predict the SM enhanced by circumferential grooved CT accurately. For the axial slot CTs, even relatively accurate results can only be obtained through both steady and unsteady simulations, which adds further complexity to the design process.

Consequently, a more reliable framework for CT design is essential. Based on the discovery of stall precursor [4], Sun et al. [5,6] proposed the stall precursor suppressed casing treatment (SPSCT) and active control[7], which improve the stall margin of the compressor by the wave-vortex interaction. This kind of CT is also called unsteady CT or impedance boundary condition CT. In our past work, unsteady CTs were modeled using a specific impedance value. Additionally, based on global stability analysis [8]. We established two key tools: a stall inception prediction method that accounts for CT effects, and an impedance boundary condition optimization method. Furthermore, we proposed an expectation for designing the impedance boundary condition CT based on the specific impedance value[8,9].

In this work, an unsteady CT design framework is developed to respond our expectation based on the resolvent analysis and impedance modelling. This framework is systematically introduced and validated with a slotted perforated plate and annular chamber CT. This manuscript is organized as follows: Firstly, a description of resolvent analysis within the compressor is presented. Second, we introduce the design process of the SPSCT. Third, the experimental data and theoretical results are presented to verify the reliability and effectiveness of the proposed CT design method. Finally, the conclusions are summarized.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Basic process of CT design

The design process of the unsteady CT can be divided into several key steps, as illustrated in FIGURE 1. These steps are described in detail in the following section.

FIGURE 1: DESIGN PROCESS

First, the selection of computational domain is done, followed by mesh generation. The steady flow field is then obtained using the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations. Subsequently, the three-dimensional steady flow field is converted to the meridional surface, and the treatment is presented below,

$$\bar{q}(r, z) = \frac{\int_{\theta_p}^{\theta_s} \rho(r, \theta, z) q(r, \theta, z) d\theta}{(\theta_s - \theta_p) \bar{\rho}}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ and q represent the density and flow parameters, respectively. θ_s and θ_p are the left and right boundary of the computational domain.

Second, impedance boundary condition optimization, the optimization is based on the compressor stall inception prediction method and resolvent analysis method [8]. The stability analysis model is described. For the flow mechanics problem within the compressor, the Navier-Stokes equations can be transformed as,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{Q}) \quad (2)$$

Eq.(2) can be linearized into the perturbation form, it can be presented as,

$$\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{q}}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{L}(\bar{\mathbf{Q}}) \hat{\mathbf{q}}. \quad (3)$$

We introduce the proper boundary conditions and harmonic solution of $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ into the Eq.(3), and we can get the generalized eigenvalue equation,

$$\mathbf{A} \hat{\mathbf{q}} = \omega \mathbf{B} \hat{\mathbf{q}}. \quad (4)$$

The Eq.(4) can be solved by the Arnoldi method, and the eigenvalue ω and eigenvector $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ can be used to analyze the

stability of the compressor system and distribution of the perturbation mode.

Next, we will describe the resolvent analysis method. For the generalized eigenvalue equation, we introduce a forcing term $\hat{\mathbf{f}}$ to model the nonlinear terms or any exogenous forcing, the Eq.(4) can be transformed into

$$\mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{q}} = \omega\mathbf{M}\hat{\mathbf{q}} + \hat{\mathbf{f}}, \quad (5)$$

After some mathematical treatment, we can get

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}} = (\mathbf{A} - \omega\mathbf{M})^{-1} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{f}}. \quad (6)$$

Among them, the $(\mathbf{A} - \omega\mathbf{M})^{-1}$ can be called the resolvent operator, which also can be considered as the reduced order model (ROM) of the flow system. The singular value decomposition is used to solve the resolvent operator,

$$\mathbf{H}_{q,\omega}^{-1} = \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{m,\omega} \cdot \Sigma \cdot \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{m,\omega}^*. \quad (7)$$

Then, we can obtain the forcing mode $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{m,\omega}$, response mode $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{m,\omega}$ and energy gain, Σ is the matrix of singular value, the first order singular value is named after energy gain. $\mathbf{H}_{q,\omega}^{-1}$ is the standard resolvent operator. As so far, the ROM is established. Next, we use the ROM to evaluate the compressor system response under specific forcing or boundary condition input.

Third, impedance boundary condition optimization. The established ROM [5] treats various forcing or boundary conditions as input perturbations. The energy gain of this linear system, which quantifies disturbance amplification and serves as the system response to these inputs.

The impedance boundary condition is treated as the input to the ROM. From this framework, the minimum energy gain within the impedance complex plane is derived, and the optimal impedance value within the compressor can be obtained.

Fourth, impedance model. Acoustic impedance models for the perforated plates in unsteady CTs can be developed via computational acoustics simulations or flow duct experiments.

Then, reverse design of the CT is performed based on the optimized impedance value and the developed impedance model. Specifically, the optimized impedance values and relevant flow conditions are input into the impedance model, which outputs the corresponding CT geometric parameters.

So far, the optimized CT geometric parameters are derived. These parameters can then be validated through experiments or unsteady numerical simulations.

2.2 Impedance model

In last subsection, we introduce the basic process of unsteady CT design. this subsection focuses on the development of the impedance model. In order to validate the reliability of the

proposed design method, the CT conFIGUREuration featuring a slotted perforated plate and an annular chamber is selected as the target case. When flow passes through the slot, wave-vortex interaction is induced, thereby enhancing the stall margin of the compressor. The FIGUREuration is depicted in FIGURE 2.

FIGURE 2: ONE TYPE OF UNSTEADY CT [6]

In this work, we assume that the CT exhibits locally reactive behavior in the axial direction and nonlocally reactive behavior in the circumferential direction. For each circumferential mode number, the ratio of acoustic pressure to acoustic particle velocity is associated with $\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial r}$, and its radial distribution is defined by the radial characteristic function, and is independent on the azimuthal angle. Thus, impedance (a locally defined quantity) can be employed to model the unsteady effects of the annular chamber.

The impedance of this CT depends on frequency and circumferential mode number, and it can be defined as $Z(m, \omega)$. Furthermore, the total impedance can be decomposed into two components, one corresponding to the perforated plate and the other to the chamber,

$$Z(m, \omega) = Z_p(\omega) + Z_c(m, \omega), \quad (8)$$

where Z_p denotes the impedance of the slotted perforated plate, and Z_c is the impedance of the annular back-chamber. Next, we describe the modeling process for both the perforated plate and the annular chamber.

A. Impedance model of perforated plate

The impedance of a perforated plate can typically be decomposed into the sum of a no-flow component Z_{nf} and a flow-contributed component Z_f , as expressed below,

$$Z_p = Z_{nf} + Z_f. \quad (9)$$

The impedance of the no-flow component can be derived theoretically and refined through experimental correction. For validation, the perforated plate conFIGUREuration illustrated in

FIGURE 2 is isolated, and its detailed structure is presented in FIGURE 3.

FIGURE 3: CONFIGUREURATION OF UNSTEADY CT

Firstly, we will introduce the impedance of no-flow component. Maa [10] developed a slit impedance model based on the narrow slit hypothesis, where the total impedance of a slit is the sum of the slit body impedance and the edge impedance. the formulas for the slit body impedance and edge impedance are presented below,

$$Z_{slit} = \frac{\Delta \hat{p}}{\hat{u}} = i\omega\rho_0 t_p \left[1 - \frac{\tanh(s\sqrt{i})}{s\sqrt{i}} \right]^{-1}, \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{cases} R_{edge} = \frac{\sqrt{2\omega\rho_0\mu}}{2} \\ X_{edge} = \frac{0.5\omega F(e) w_s}{c_0} \end{cases}, \quad (11)$$

where Z_{slit} is the slit body impedance, R_{edge} and X_{edge} represent the real and imaginary parts of the edge impedance, respectively. $\Delta \hat{p}$ is the fluctuating pressure difference across the perforated plate, \hat{u} is the acoustic particle velocity, s is $\frac{w_s}{2} \sqrt{i\omega\rho_0/\mu}$, and $F(e)$ is the elliptic integral,

$$F(e) = \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \theta}} d\theta \quad (12)$$

To validate the reliability of the impedance model, an impedance tube experiment is conducted, and the experimental setup is shown in FIGURE 4. The perforated plate used in the tests is shown in FIGURE 5. For the acoustic pressure measurement within the impedance tube, the four-microphone method is adopted.

FIGURE 4: IMPEDANCE TUBE

FIGURE 5: PERFORATED PLATE SAMPLE

Since the slot profile differs from the narrow slit assumed in Maa's model, the edge impedance model is corrected. The revised formula is presented below,

$$\begin{cases} R_{edge} = 2 \frac{L_s}{w_s} \frac{\sqrt{2}\mu s}{w_s} \\ X_{edge} = i\omega\rho_0 (1.7\sqrt{\sigma} w_s F(e)) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The geometric parameters of partial test sample are listed in TABLE 1, and the comparison between experimental results (EXP), modified model and Maa model are presented in FIGURE 6.

TABLE 1: PERFORATED PLATE GEOMETRY PARAMETERS

Sample	t_p (mm)	w_s (mm)	L_s (mm)	σ
1	6	7.3	41	0.0398
2	9	4.6	41	0.0267
3	15	7.3	41	0.0398
4	9	4.6	69.7	0.0454

(c) Sample 3 (d) Sample 4
 FIGURE 6: COMPARISON BETWEEN MAA MODEL, MODIFIED MODEL AND EXPERIMENTS.

The modified model enhance the predictive capability of Maa's original model: in most cases, the discrepancy between the modified model and experimental results is smaller than that of the original Maa model. Thus, the modified Maa model is employed to predict the no-flow impedance of the perforated plate.

Next, the modeling process for the flow-contributed impedance of the slotted perforated plate is described. Given the complex flow conditions in the blade tip region, the combined effects of flow must be incorporated into the flow-contributed impedance model. Numerical simulations are used to develop this model, and the corresponding computational model [11] is illustrated in FIGURE 7.

FIGURE 7: ACOUSTIC COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

Flow parameters are decomposed into mean and perturbation components, and the frequency-domain linearized Navier-Stokes (LNSF) equations are used to discretize the computational domain. The impedance of this perforated plate can be treated as the difference of input impedance and radiation acoustic impedance of the slot. Ingard and Singal [12] validated that, for a piston radiating in a moving medium, the effect of grazing flow is negligible when the Mach number is below 0.2. This implies that the radiation impedance is approximately identical in cases with and without grazing flow. Thus, the flow-contributed impedance can be derived as below,

$$Z_f = Z_i - Z_{nf,i} \quad (14)$$

where Z_f is flow-contributed impedance value, Z_i and $Z_{nf,i}$ are the input impedance with/without grazing flow, respectively. pressure data are extracted from seven numerically placed probes with non-uniform spacing, their locations are 40mm, 70mm, 170mm, 310mm, 365mm, 410mm, 565mm, respectively. These probe positions meet the frequency range requirements of this study (30hz to 930hz). The extracted data

can be substituted into Eq. (15) to derive the flow-contributed impedance under grazing-bias flow effects.

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \hat{p}(y_1) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{p}(y_7) \end{bmatrix}}_{\hat{p}_{mm}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} e^{i(\omega t - k^+ y_1)} & e^{i(\omega t + k^+ y_1)} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ e^{i(\omega t - k^+ y_7)} & e^{i(\omega t + k^+ y_7)} \end{bmatrix}}_M \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} p^+ \\ p^- \end{bmatrix}}_{p^\pm} \quad (15)$$

The formulas for the normalized flow-contributed resistance and reactance are presented below,

$$\begin{cases} r_{flow} = \frac{r - r_0}{Ma_0} \\ x_{flow} = \frac{x - x_0}{k w_s} \end{cases}, \quad (16)$$

where r and x are the specific resistance and reactance under grazing flow, and the subscript flow and 0 indicates the impedance with/without flow, respectively. k is the wave number ω/c . The Strouhal number $St = k w_s c_0 / U_0$ is used to represent the nondimensional frequency. Firstly, the reliability of the LNSF method is validated. Moers et al. [13] conducted experiments on shear flow and combined flow, providing detailed experimental data and geometric parameters. The basic geometric parameters of their test configuration are listed in TABLE 2, and a comparison between the experimental results and numerical computations is illustrated in FIGURE 8. The results indicate that the LNSF method can capture the fundamental trend of flow-contributed impedance in both Case 1 and 2. Despite this, in Case 1, at small Strouhal numbers (St), the computed reactance overpredicts the experimental measurements. For Case 2, the LNSF method accurately captures the trend and amplitude of both resistance and reactance, except at a Strouhal number of 0.45, where the LNSF prediction deviates significantly from the experimental results. Overall, the LNSF method is validated and can be used to compute the impedance of the perforated plate under various flow conditions.

TABLE 2: BASIC PARAMETERS [13]

	t_p (mm)	w_s (mm)	L_s (mm)	U_0 (m/s)	U_b (m/s)
1	15	10	5	16.8	0
2	15	10	5	16.8	-14.1

FIGURE 8 Comparison between experiments and LNSF in Cases 1 and 2.

Firstly, simulations of pure grazing flow cases were conducted. We set the different t_p , w_s , L_s , and σ as the tested geometric parameters, and the grazing flow Ma is set to 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2. The t_p is [6, 15] mm, w_s is [3.5, 7.3] mm, L_s is [2.05, 5.0] mm, and σ is [3.68, 14.7]%. The flow-contributed resistance and reactance under grazing flow are shown in FIGURE 9. For the flow-contributed resistance r_{flow} , its distribution is relatively smooth with no significant fluctuations, allowing direct fitting of these data points using a high-order function. By contrast, the flow-contributed reactance x_{flow} exhibits obvious fluctuations at St ranging from 0 to 0.5, beyond this range, x_{flow} gradually approaches zero as St increases. To address this, the marked data points (marked in red) are excluded, and the remaining points are fitted to a separate curve.

FIGURE 9: FLOW-CONTRIBUTED IMPEDANCE AND FITTING CURVE.

At this point, we can obtain the total impedance of the perforated plate, which is the sum of no-flow component Z_{nf} and flow-contributed component Z_f ,

$$Z_p = \underbrace{Z_{slit} + Z_{edge}}_{Z_{nf}} + \underbrace{Ma_0 r_{flow} + k_0 w_s x_{flow}}_{Z_f}, \quad (17)$$

An additional LNSF simulation is conducted, and its geometric parameters are set to $t_p = 8mm$, $w_s = 5.7mm$, $L_s = 41mm$ and $\sigma = 8.82\%$. A comparison between the flow-contributed impedance Z_f obtained from LNSF and that calculated via the fitting formula is illustrated in FIGURE 10. The results demonstrate that the fitting curve effectively captures the fundamental trend of flow-contributed impedance under grazing flow in this work. Consequently, the fitting formula will be employed to compute the impedance of the perforated plate under grazing flow.

FIGURE 10: COMPARISON BETWEEN FITTING CURVE AND LNSF.

Given the complex flow conditions in blade tip region of the compressor, as shown in FIGURE 11. The effects of this grazing-bias flow are critical to the impedance model. The tip flow field exerts a significant influence on the impedance of the unsteady CTs. In the following, the grazing-bias flow effects will be incorporated into the developed flow-contributed fitting formula.

FIGURE 11: STEADY FLOW FIELD.

Sun et al. [14] proposed a discharge coefficient method to predict the resistance under grazing-bias flow conditions. In their experimental work, acoustic reactance is not significantly affected by either grazing flow or bias flow. By contrast, in the simulations conducted in this study, reactance varies with

increasing bias flow. To simplify the treatment of grazing-bias flow effects, an alternative method is adopted to derive these grazing-bias flow effects for other cases. The amplitude coefficient χ is defined,

$$\chi = \frac{Z_{c,f}}{Z_{g,f}}, \quad (18)$$

where $Z_{c,f}$ is the flow-contributed impedance under combined flow, $Z_{g,f}$ is the flow-contributed impedance under grazing flow, which is equal to Z_f . The real and imaginary components of flow-contributed impedance are depicted in FIGURE 12, and the amplitude coefficient χ is shown in FIGURE 13. The amplitude coefficient exhibits a linear functional relationship with grazing-bias flow. Once χ is determined, the acoustic impedance under combined flow can be calculated using Eq.(19) for different sets of geometric and flow parameters.

$$Z_f = Z_{c,f}(Ma_0, Ma_b, St) = \chi(Ma_0, Ma_b) \cdot Z_{g,f}(St) \quad (19)$$

(a) Resistance (b) Reactance
FIGURE 12: FLOW-CONTRIBUTED IMPEDANCE UNDER COMBINED FLOW.

(a) $\text{Re}(\chi)$ (b) $\text{Im}(\chi)$
FIGURE 13: AMPLITUDE COEFFICIENT FROM $Z_{g,f}(St)$ TO $Z_{c,f}(Ma_0, Ma_b, St)$.

An additional numerical simulation was conducted to compare the results of the LNSF method and the combined flow

effect model. For the tested perforated plate, the geometric parameters were as follows: $w_s = 5.7$ mm, $L_s = 41$ mm, $t_p = 8$ mm, and $\sigma = 8.82\%$. The present method (interpolation method) is used to calculate the impedance value, which integrates the amplitude coefficient and the impedance under grazing flow.

For various sets of geometric parameters, this interpolation method effectively captures the trend of the LNSF results and demonstrates the ability to predict the grazing-bias flow effect across different grazing-to-bias flow velocity ratios. While a discrepancy in resistance is observed near 400 Hz between the two methods, this difference is acceptable for the scope of this study. Notably, the dominant frequency range relevant to the compressor's stall margin improvement is limited to the rotor rotating frequency, which does not overlap with the 400 Hz region of discrepancy.

(a) Resistance (b) Reactance
FIGURE 14: COMPARISON BETWEEN COEFFICIENT AMPLITUDE AND LNSF.

B. Impedance model of annular chamber

Thus far, the modeling process for the perforated plate has been described. Next, the impedance model of the annular chamber is introduced. the annular chamber is depicted in FIGURE 15. The model is based on the following assumptions:

- Any mean axial or azimuthal flow in the chamber is neglected.
- The chamber exhibits non-local reaction in the azimuthal direction and local reaction in the axial direction.
- The circumferential mode number of the azimuthal propagating disturbance in the chamber must match that in the main duct.

(a) (b)
FIGURE 15: ANNULAR CHAMBER.

The pressure field in the groove can be expressed as,

$$\hat{p}(z, r, \theta) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-im\theta} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \hat{p}_n(z) \hat{p}_{mn}(r) \quad (20)$$

The grooves are assumed to be axially locally reacting, and the pressure \hat{p}_n can be defined as,

$$\hat{p}_n(z) = A_n \cos(k_n z) + B_n \sin(k_n z), k_n = \frac{n\pi}{l_g} \quad (21)$$

For the tested compressor, the cutoff frequency required for the first axial mode is 717Hz. the shroud and hub diameters are 0.6 m and 0.42 m, respectively. In this study, only the case of $n = 0$ is considered, and the axial length of CT is smaller than the wavelength of the tested frequency. The radial propagation of pressure within the chamber is governed by the Bessel function,

$$\hat{p}_{mn}(r) = C J_m(\alpha_n r) + D Y_m(\alpha_n r), \quad (22)$$

where $J_m(\cdot)$ and $Y_m(\cdot)$ are the Bessel functions of the first and second kind, respectively. For $n = 0$, the dispersion relation simplifies to $\alpha_n = \pm \sqrt{k^2 - k_n^2} = k$, where k is the wave number. The boundary condition is specified as a hard wall, and the radial particle velocity can be derived as follows,

$$u_{r_n}(r) = \frac{i\alpha_n}{k} [J'_m(kr) + K_{mn} Y'_m(kr)] \quad (23)$$

Introducing the hard wall boundary condition at the bottom of annular chamber,

$$\left. \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R+h} = 0. \quad (24)$$

Then,

$$C = -D \frac{Y'_m[k(R+h)]}{J'_m[k(R+h)]}, \quad (25)$$

It is assumed that the acoustic particle velocities at surface 1 and surface 2 are equal in FIGURE 15, it satisfies the velocity continuity condition $v_{r,1} = v_{r,2}$, from which the following relation can be derived,

$$v_r = iD \left[-\frac{Y'_m[k(R+h)]}{J'_m[k(R+h)]} J'_m(kR) + Y'_m(kR) \right] \quad (26)$$

Furthermore, another boundary condition, the acoustic pressure continuous condition can be incorporated,

$$\hat{p}_{duct} - \hat{p}_c = Z_{slot} \cdot v_r. \quad (27)$$

The expression of \hat{p}_c can be depicted as,

$$\hat{p}_c = -D \frac{Y'_m[k(R+h)]}{J'_m[k(R+h)]} J'_m(kR) + D Y'_m(kR), \quad (28)$$

and we have,

$$\hat{p}_{duct}/v_r = Z_{slot} + \hat{p}_c/v_r. \quad (29)$$

The impedance of the annular chamber $Z_{chamber}(m, \omega)$ can be depicted as,

$$Z_{chamber}(m, \omega) = \frac{J'_m(kR) + K_m Y'_m(kR)}{i [J'_m(kR) + K_m Y'_m(kR)]}, K_m = -\frac{J'_m[k(R+h)]}{Y'_m[k(R+h)]} \quad (30)$$

where R is the shroud radius and h denotes the cavity depth. Next, numerical simulations were conducted to compare the results of the LNSF method and the developed impedance model $Z_{chamber}(m, \omega)$. The results are illustrated in FIGURE 16 for a circumferential mode number of 1 and a frequency of 500Hz, with varying normalized cavity depths tested. The computed $Z_{chamber}$ is defined as $\frac{p}{v}|_{chamber}$. The theoretical results capture the distribution of the $Z_{chamber}(1, 500\text{Hz})$ under the proposed assumption.

FIGURE 16: COMPARISON BETWEEN IMPEDANCE MODEL.

In summary, the impedance model for the slotted perforated plate and annular chamber under grazing-bias flow have been fully established. The total impedance value of unsteady CT is expressed as follows,

$$Z_{CT} = Z_{nf}(\omega, t_p, L_s, w_s) + \underbrace{\chi(Ma_0, Ma_b)}_{Z_f} \cdot Z_{g,f}(\omega) + Z_c(\omega, m, h, R) \quad (31)$$

From Eq.(31), it can be seen that the impedance of Z_{CT} is dependent on the following factors: geometric parameters of perforated plate and annular chamber, frequency, circumferential mode number, main flow and bias flow conditions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the previous section, the design process and impedance modeling process for the unsteady CT are described. In this section, experiments are conducted on a low-speed compressor to validate the aforementioned unsteady CT design method. The experimental test rig employs the low-speed single-stage compressor TA36 [6], and its steady characteristics are depicted in FIGURE 17. The geometry parameters of low-speed compressor TA36 is listed in TABLE 3.

TABLE 3: BASIC PARAMETERS OF TA36

PARAMETER	Rotor	Stator
Rotating speed	2930	0
Tip clearance	0.6	0.5
Blade angle	60	7
Blade number	20	27
Aspect ratio	1.18	1.40
Shroud diameter	600	600
Hub diameter	346	401
Hub ratio	0.58	0.67
Solidity	1.45/1.51/1.87	1.10/1.24/1.53

FIGURE 17 STEADY CHARACTERISTICS.

The numerical simulations capture the fundamental trend of the experimental results, and can serve as the base flow for constructing the ROM. The geometric parameters of the SPSCT are listed in TABLE 4, where the unit of length is millimeters. The discussion will be organized into several subsections to validate the reliability of the theoretical method.

TABLE 4: SPSCT GEOMETRY PARAMETERS

Type	Basic parameters				
Chamber depth	0	5	55	95	115
Chamber axial length	100		120		
Plate thickness	15				
Slot width	4		6		
Slot length	50		70		
Slot number	24		30		
Perforated ratio %	6.4		7.5		

Since the CT is intended to improve the stall margin of the compressor, the CT design is also conducted near the stall inception points. The operating conditions p_1 and p_2 are selected for this study. Additionally, previous research [8,15,16] has identified the first circumferential mode as the most unstable mode in the compressor; thus, the CT design is focused on this circumferential mode number.

The sensitive frequencies are calculated based on the first circumferential mode, with the results illustrated in FIGURE 18. The most sensitive frequencies for p_1 and p_2 are 0.64 and 0.79, respectively. These two frequencies, combined with the first circumferential mode, constitute the target operating conditions at p_1 and p_2 .

FIGURE 18: ENERGY GAIN SPECTRUM AT OPERATING CONDITION p_1 AND p_2 .

The energy gain spectrum across the complex impedance plane with first circumferential mode number and their corresponding sensitive frequencies, are computed and depicted in FIGURE 19. The energy gain spectrum serves as a metric to evaluate the impact of impedance boundary condition on the compressor system.

(a) p_1 5.30kg/s RS=0.64 (b) p_2 5.36kg/s RS=0.79

FIGURE 19 Energy gain spectrum

Next, the theoretical method will be validated across different geometric parameters, including the presence of a cavity, cavity depth, and perforation ratio.

The existence of cavity

To investigate the influence of the annular chamber's presence, a perforated plate with the following parameters was tested: $L_s = 75$ mm, $w_s = 4$ mm, $t_p = 15$ mm, and $\sigma = 7.68\%$. Two cases were compared: one with a cavity depth of 0 mm (no cavity) and another with a cavity depth of 55 mm. The measured steady characteristics are illustrated in FIGURE 20. For each case, the geometric parameters and flow parameters are input into the impedance model Eq.(31), and the corresponding impedance values are derived, as shown in FIGURE 21. A cavity depth of 0.0005 mm in the theoretical method is used as a practical approximation for a zero cavity depth. As shown in FIGURE 22, the theoretical energy gain captures the fundamental trend of how the cavity affects the measured stall inception points.

FIGURE 20 STEADY CHARACTERISTIC OF THE COMPRESSOR WITH/WITHOUT THE CAVITY.

(a) Resistance (b) Reactance
FIGURE 21 IMPEDANCE VALUE

FIGURE 22 COMPARISON BETWEEN ENERGY GAIN AND MEASURED STALL INCEPTION POINTS.

The influence of cavity depth

The influence of varying cavity depths is investigated, and the steady characteristics are illustrated in FIGURE 23. The geometric and flow parameters are input into the impedance model, and the resulting impedance values are shown in FIGURE 24.

FIGURE 23 STEADY CHARACTERISTIC OF THE COMPRESSOR WITH DIFFERENT CAVITY DEPTHS.

(a) Resistance (b) Reactance
FIGURE 24 IMPEDANCE VALUE.

The operating condition p_2 is selected as the observation point. The impedance values mentioned above are input into the impedance boundary optimization method, and the corresponding energy gains are derived, as shown in FIGURE 25. The computed energy gain captures the trend of the stall inception points, including the inflection point.

FIGURE 25: COMPARISON BETWEEN ENERGY GAIN AND MEASURED STALL INCEPTION POINTS WITH DIFFERENT CAVITY DEPTH.

The influence of perforated ratio

Next, the influence of the SPSCT's perforation ratio is investigated. Its geometry parameters are fixed as follow, cavity axial length is 120mm, cavity depth is 65mm, slot chord length L_s is 50mm, slot width w_s is 6mm, plate thickness t_p is 15mm. Two perforation ratios are tested: 5.6% and 12%. The steady characteristics of the compressor are illustrated in FIGURE 26. Additionally, the geometric and flow parameters are input into the impedance model, with the corresponding impedance values shown in FIGURE 27. The energy gain and the measured stall mass flow points are shown in FIGURE 28.

FIGURE 26: STEADY CHARACTERISTIC WITH DIFFERENT PERFORATED RATIO AND SW CASES.

(a) Resistance (b) Reactance
FIGURE 27: IMPEDANCE VALUE.

FIGURE 28: COMPARISON BETWEEN ENERGY GAIN AND MEASURED STALL INCEPTION POINTS.

Based on the comparison presented above, the results demonstrate that the established theoretical design method for the CT of slotted perforated plate and annular chamber is capable of accounting for variations in key geometric parameters. These comparisons validate that the theoretical design method can effectively evaluate the energy gain associated with specific CT geometric parameters. This capability, in turn, enables designers to conduct targeted stall margin improvement design for compressors, directly linking CT geometry optimization to enhanced compressor stability.

4. CONCLUSION

This work establishes a design framework for unsteady CTs based on the developed ROM. The CT featuring a slotted perforated plate and an annular chamber is used to validate the design method. Its corresponding impedance model is developed by combining the LNSF method and experiments.

Experiments are conducted on the compressor equipped with the unsteady CT, and the experimental results are compared with the theoretical predictions. The theoretical results effectively capture the trend of stall mass flow points of the compressor across variations in the geometric parameters of CT. Notably, the design method quantifies the relationship between impedance value, energy gain, stall mass flow points and SM improvement. This capability bridges the gap between impedance values and geometric parameters of the unsteady CT, enabling the translation of target impedance requirements into actionable CT design specifications. Future work will focus on the universality of this design method on different compressors.

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